

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D6.3 - MEMORANDUMS OF ADHESION

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Executive Summary

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action co-founded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims to deploy a **new clustering governance** for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET is justified to deploy Energy Transition (ET) in public sector, for which the following challenges are targeted:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments.
- Enhancing decision-making process in deployment of ET projects.
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented.
- Encouraging the digitalization of measures and plans.
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.
- Building capacity of local authorities.

All these targeted objectives will give the needed support for the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

The present report outlines the vital role of the Memorandum of Adhesion (MoA) in facilitating collaboration, aligning objectives, and institutionalizing the engagement of participating entities in the ePLANET project during the pilot and the replicability phase. The various stages taken in the development of the documents are presented, as well as their final versions and the current number of signatories.

The main findings were:

- The Memorandum of Adhesion supports the establishment of a framework for collaboration, alignment, and coordinated action among ePLANET's participating authorities, promoting the effective implementation of energy transition plans, and achieving sustainable energy goals.
- Two types of MoA were developed, one to be applied and signed by local and regional authorities during the pilot phase of the project and another with some modifications to be applied during the replication phase of the project.
- 199 MoAs were signed until the submission of this deliverable.
- The MoA is a forerunner of the “ePLANET Joint Agreement” to be signed towards the end of the project, between all involved parties, reflecting a joint vision on actions and initiatives to accelerate achievement of energy transition targets.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CIMNE	International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering
CRES	Centre for Renewable Sources and Saving
DDGI	Girona Provincial Council
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ICLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion
PA	Public Authority
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Local and regional authorities play a key role in the EU's pursuit of carbon neutrality by 2050. Decentralized governance structures, such as those led by local and regional authorities, are better equipped to mobilize, and engage local stakeholders, fostering a bottom-up approach to the clean energy transition and significantly accelerating the deployment of renewable energy technologies. This highlights the need for local and regional authorities to effectively commit to and plan for the transition to clean energy.

Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments is one of the main challenges in achieving Energy Transition objectives, as it enables optimal decision-making, coherence, and consistent implementation of measures in towns and cities. Additionally, the heterogeneity of current EU local authority platforms for managing Energy Transition results in information loss and difficulties in data sharing and community engagement.

The ePLANET project targets the deployment of a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information.

ePLANET aims to facilitate and ease the deployment of coordinated energy transition actions by the public sector. The project utilizes innovative big data tools and an advanced clustering governance approach to enhance Energy Transition Plans at the municipal level. Besides, it fosters the digitalisation of energy data available in dispersed data sources, energy transition measures and Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs), enabling an ecosystem of data and tools to support decision-making on energy transition.

ePLANET's main objectives are:

- To define and establish a transparent and coherent information sharing framework among public authorities.
- To deploy multi-level working groups of related public authorities and stakeholders for sharing of information and to enable a collaborative approach in development and updating of Energy Transition plans.
- To enable digitalization of the energy transition plans of the public authorities as base for coherence, sharing, coordination and integration.
- To support new adopters and consolidate existing networks.
- To institutionalize ePLANET networks and multi-level working groups.

Through the ePLANET project, the collaboration on the energy transition between public authorities will be institutionalized, resulting in various impacts, including the signing of 603 Memorandums of Adhesion (MoA).

1.1 Organisation of the deliverable

The first section introduces the ePLANET project, emphasizing its objectives and expected impacts, mentioning the signing of the MoA as one of the project's main goals.

In section 2, the development process of the MoA is described (one for the pilot phase and another for the replication phase), from the initial design to the final versions approved by the consortium partners, in particular the pilot regions.

Section 3 presents the current scenario of MoA signature collection, breaking it down by pilot and follower regions.

The fourth section concludes this deliverable, providing a comprehensive summary and insightful remarks encapsulating the key implications discovered throughout the document.

2 Development of the Memorandums of Adhesion

To formalize the commitment in utilizing the outcomes of ePLANET, a MoA must be signed by all participating local and regional authorities involved in ePLANET activities across different project stages, including the follower Public Authorities (PAs) beyond the pilot territories.

The MoA is an instrument for engagement of the local and regional authorities to participate actively in the ePLANET project activities, exploit the ePLANET project tools and outcomes, and to strengthen multi-level governance cooperation between local, regional, and national authorities.

The expected total number of signed MoA during the project lifetime is 603, divided into regional (32) and local authorities (571).

Table 2-1 summarises the expected number of signed MoAs during the testing and pilot deployment phase of the project.

Table 2-1 - Number of signed MoAs during the pilot phase

	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín Region	Total
Local authorities	16	67	61	144
Regional authorities	1	1	1	3

Table 2-2 presents the figures related to the expected signed MoAs during the second phase of the project, when transfer and expansion will take place.

Table 2-2 - Number of signed MoAs during the replicability phase

	Scale-up at regional / national level			Other EU regions	Total
	Greece	Catalonia	Czech Republic		
Local authorities	60	145	119	101	425
Regional authorities	6	4	7	12	29

The discussions for the development of the MoA started at the end of M5 (January 2022), when CRES, CIMNE and ICLEI had dedicated meetings and presented their ideas on the format and requirements of the respective document.

Initially, CIMNE presented a MoA template used in other similar activities carried out in the province of Catalonia. However, given the very extensive format of the document and the effort needed to translate it from Catalan into English, a different approach was chosen, focussing on something more concise and avoiding unnecessary elements, but at the same time precise and preventing uncertainty in the mind of the local or regional authorities.

During the following months, CRES, as the WP leader, and ICLEI, responsible for task 6.2, jointly drafted a first version, seeking to include the most important points related to the MoA highlighted in the Grant Agreement (GA) and at the same time moulding them in a way that would be easily understood by local and regional authorities, motivating them to sign it.

On M10 (June 2022), the first version was presented during a project meeting and feedback was given from representatives of the three pilot regions: EAZK, DDGI, and RDFC. Even though a two-and-a-half-page document was put forward, it was decided that its content could be further reduced and clarifications on the main points described in the GA could be made in a more objective way.

In the end, the consortium partners agreed to have the following points as the main responsibilities / obligations of the signatories:

- Participate in ePLANET networking, capacity building and dissemination events.
- Provide feedback to support the development of the ePLANET platform and governance innovations.
- Exploit the ePLANET tools and other project outcomes, promoting their implementation within the region, municipalities, and other interested stakeholders in the territory.
- Utilize the holistic methodology developed in the ePLANET project.
- Seek synergies between ePLANET and other relevant projects and initiatives implemented in the territory.

In relation to those signatures collected in the second phase of the project, i.e., the replicability phase, the following points were added:

- Support the promotion of the ePLANET Joint Agreement.
- Consider the Policy recommendations at the EU level that will be developed by ePLANET, towards future development and/or update of our local / regional energy policies.

Still, at the end of M10, a new round of review with the pilot regions was carried out and it was agreed that the document, now one page long, was satisfactory. Discussions regarding the validity of digital signatures as well as translated versions into local languages (Czech, Greek and Catalan) were held and it was decided to add some wording on this at the end of the documents.

The final version of the MoA, one for the pilot phase and one for the replication phase, were made available to all partners on 22 July in the project document repository. The final versions are presented in Annexes 1 and 2.

It was proposed that the collection of signatures be carried out during dissemination events or replication/networking events to ensure wide visibility and promotion.

2.1 Systematization of the Memorandums of Adhesion

For systematically collecting and sorting signed MoAs a set of folders/registers were created at the ePLANET repository. The structure and hierarchy of signed MoAs registers is designed according to the ePLANET GA to ensure classification, recording, and organising signed MoAs.

Table 2-3 presents the Catalogue of Registers of signed MoAs.

Table 2-3 - Catalogue of Registers of signed MoAs

ID number	Register File	Register
1	MoA_Register_01	Phase 1: Testing and Pilot Deployment Pilot Territory - Crete Island
2	MoA_Register_02	Phase 1: Testing and Pilot Deployment Pilot Territory - Girona Province
3	MoA_Register_03	Phase 1: Testing and Pilot Deployment Pilot Territory - Zlin Region
4	MoA_Register_04_1	Phase 2: Transferring and Expansion Pilot Regions Scaleup - National Level Greece
5	MoA_Register_04_2	Phase 2: Transferring and Expansion Pilot Regions Scaleup - National Level Catalonia
6	MoA_Register_04_3	Phase 2: Transferring and Expansion Pilot Regions Scaleup - National Level Czech Republic
7	MoA_Register_05	Phase 2: Transferring and Expansion Other European Union Regions - Public Authorities
8	MoA_Register_06	Phase 2: Transferring and Expansion Follower Regions (through an Open Call process)

The Catalogue of Registers consists of 8 registers, 3 registers for collecting and systematization of signed MoAs at the Phase 1 “Testing and Pilot Deployment” and 5 registers for collecting and systematization of signed MoAs at the Phase 2 “Transferring and Expansion”. Classification of registers is based on the geographic location characteristics of the ePLANET pilot, i.e.:

- Phase 1: ePLANET pilot territory.
- Phase 2: ePLANET pilot regions.
- Phase 2: Other European Union regions.
- Phase 2: ePLANET follower regions.

Figure 2-1 presents the navigation tree of Registers of signed MoAs.

Figure 2-1 - Navigation tree of Registers of signed MoAs

The main objective of the navigation tree is to help users of Registers of signed ePLANET MoAs to navigate relevant register entities efficiently. The navigation tree is created following the principles of register user-friendliness offering to users an option to save the signed MoA, find the signed MoA they need, monitor the progress of collecting the signed MoAs, etc.

3 Status of signed Memorandums of Adhesion

3.1 Zlín Region

Located in the eastern part of the Czech Republic, the Zlín Region has a population of approximately 590,000 inhabitants. The region covers an area of about 3,964 square kilometres and is comprised of 307 municipalities, encompassing cities, towns, and villages situated within the region.

The Zlín Region pilot focus on 61 municipalities and around 119 more municipalities are expected to engage during ePLANET's scale-up and replicability phase.

Table 3-1 presents the details of the public authorities that have signed the MoA at present.

Table 3-1 - Status of signed MoAs in the Zlín Region

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
1	Obec Topolná	Topolná (CZ)	30/09/2022
2	Obec Slavkov pod Hostýnem	Slavkov pod Hostýnem (CZ)	25/10/2022
3	Obec Jarcová	Jarcová (CZ)	30/11/2022
4	Obec Horní Bečva	Horní Bečva (CZ)	30/11/2022
5	Obec Vlčnov	Vlčnov (CZ)	30/11/2022
6	Obec Brusné	Brusné (CZ)	06/12/2022
7	Obec Kvasice	Kvasice (CZ)	06/12/2022
8	Obec Bařice-Velké Těšany	Bařice-Velké Těšany (CZ)	06/12/2022
9	Obec Hutisko-Solanec	Hutisko-Solanec (CZ)	06/12/2022
10	Městys Nový Hrozenkov	Nový Hrozenkov (CZ)	06/12/2022
11	Obec Dolní Němčí	Dolní Němčí (CZ)	08/12/2022
12	Obec Březolupy	Březolupy (CZ)	08/12/2022
13	Obec Kašava	Kašava (CZ)	12/12/2022
14	Obec Jasenná	Jasenná (CZ)	12/12/2022

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
15	Obec Horní Němčí	Horní Němčí (CZ)	09/12/2022
16	Zlínský Kraj	Zlín (CZ)	13/12/2022
17	Obec Huslenky	Huslenky (CZ)	16/12/2022
18	MAS Východní Slovácko, z.s.	Suchá Loz (CZ)	16/12/2022
19	Obec Bánov	Bánov (CZ)	16/12/2022
20	Městys Pozlovice	Pozlovice (CZ)	16/12/2022
21	Region Bílé Karpaty	Zlín (CZ)	16/12/2022
22	Město Slavičín	Slavičín (CZ)	02/01/2023
23	Město Bojkovice	Bojkovice (CZ)	04/01/2023
24	Obec Bystřička	Bystřička (CZ)	04/01/2023
25	Město Zubří	Zubří (CZ)	04/01/2023
26	Obec Hovězí	Hovězí (CZ)	06/01/2023
27	Město Valašské Klobouky	Valašské Klobouky (CZ)	03/01/2023
28	Obec Rusava	Rusava (CZ)	31/01/2023
29	Obec Bohuslavice nad Vláří	Bohuslavice nad Vláří (CZ)	01/02/2023
30	Obec Dolní Bečva	Dolní Bečva (CZ)	01/02/2023
31	Obec Valašská Bystřice	Valašská Bystřice (CZ)	01/02/2023
32	Obec Žlutava	Žlutava (CZ)	01/02/2023
33	Obec Podolí	Podolí (CZ)	02/02/2023
34	Obec Hřivínův Újezd	Hřivínův Újezd (CZ)	02/02/2023
35	Obec Pohořelice	Pohořelice (CZ)	03/02/2023
36	Obec Halenkovice	Halenkovice (CZ)	03/02/2023
37	Město Brumov-Bylnice	Brumov-Bylnice (CZ)	01/02/2023

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
38	Obec Petrůvka	Petrůvka (CZ)	01/02/2023
39	Město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm (CZ)	03/02/2023
40	Obec Hrobice	Hrobice (CZ)	03/02/2023
41	Obec Žalkovice	Žalkovice (CZ)	08/02/2023
42	Obec Korytná	Korytná (CZ)	01/02/2023
43	Obec Strání	Strání (CZ)	08/02/2023
44	Obec Velký Ořechov	Velký Ořechov (CZ)	03/02/2023
45	Obec Poličná	Poličná (CZ)	03/02/2023
46	Obec Komárno	Komárno (CZ)	22/02/2023
47	Město Vizovice	Vizovice (CZ)	20/02/2023
48	Obec Štítná nad Vláří-Popov	Obec Štítná nad Vláří-Popov (CZ)	16/02/2023
49	Město Hluk	Hluk (CZ)	13/02/2023
50	Město Trnava	Trnava (SK)	23/02/2023
51	Obec Roštín	Roštín (CZ)	01/01/2023
52	Obec Vysoké Pole	Vysoké Pole (CZ)	01/03/2023
53	Obec Ublo	Ublo (CZ)	10/03/2023
54	Obec Nedakonice	Nedakonice (CZ)	08/02/2023
55	Obec Rudimov	Rudimov (CZ)	14/03/2023
56	Obec Vrbka	Vrbka (CZ)	14/03/2023
57	Město Uherský Ostroh	Uherský Ostroh (CZ)	13/01/2023
58	Obec Kostelec u Holešova	Kostelec u Holešova (CZ)	08/02/2023
59	Obec Racková	Racková (CZ)	01/03/2023

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
60	Město Karolinka	Karolinka (CZ)	22/06/2023
61	Obec Dolní Lhota	Dolní Lhota (CZ)	17/03/2023
62	Obec Slavkov	Slavkov (CZ)	27/03/2023
63	Obec Šarovy	Šarovy (CZ)	27/03/2023
64	Obec Nedašov	Nedašov (CZ)	27/03/2023
65	Obec Dřínov	Dřínov (CZ)	27/03/2023
66	Obec Chvalčov	Chvalčov (CZ)	18/04/2023
67	Obec Prakšice	Prakšice (CZ)	08/05/2023
68	Obec Nedašova Lhota	Nedašova Lhota (CZ)	09/06/2023
69	Obec Kateřinice	Kateřinice (CZ)	09/06/2023
70	Obec Bohuslavice u Zlína	Bohuslavice u Zlína (CZ)	27/03/2023
71	Obec Rokytnice	Rokytnice (CZ)	11/07/2023
72	Obec Spytihněv	Spytihněv (CZ)	12/07/2023
73	Obec Liptál	Liptál (CZ)	14/07/2023
74	Obec Horní Lhota	Horní Lhota (CZ)	18/07/2023

3.2 Crete Island

Crete is the largest and most populous of the Greek islands. Located in the southern part of the country, it has a population of approximately 625,000 inhabitants. The island covers an area of around 8,450 square kilometres and is divided into four regional units: Chania, Rethymno, Heraklion, and Lasithi. They are further subdivided into 24 municipalities in total.

During the pilot phase, Crete Island prioritizes the involvement of the 16 local authorities that have already submitted their Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs). The objective of the transferring/replicability phase is to expand the project's scope to encompass the entire island. As part of the scale-up activities, the remaining municipalities in the Crete region, as well as municipalities throughout Greece, will be actively engaged.

Table 3-2 presents the details of the public authorities that have signed the MoA until now.

Table 3-2 - Status of signed MoAs in the Crete Island

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
1	Municipality of Hersonissos	Hersonissos	01/02/2023
2	Municipality of Anogia	Anogia	06/02/2023
3	Municipality of Kantanou-Selinou	Palaiohora	08/02/2023
4	Municipality of Heraklion	Heraklion	09/02/2023
5	Municipality of Platanias	Platanias	14/02/2023
6	Municipality of Apokoronas	Vrisses	20/02/2023
7	Municipality of Chania	Chania	24/02/2023
8	Municipality of Minoa Pediada	Minoa Pediada	31/03/2023

3.3 Girona Province

The province of Girona is located in the north-eastern part of Catalonia, Spain. It has an estimated population of around 740,000 inhabitants and the province covers an area of approximately 5,900 square kilometres.

The Girona Province has 222 municipalities and the pilot focus on 67 of them. Scaling up will include around 145 more municipalities (including Catalonia ones).

Table 3-3 presents a list of the municipalities that have signed the MoA so far.

Table 3-3 - Status of signed MoAs in the Girona Province

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
1	Ajuntament d'Albons	Albons	08/11/2022
2	Ajuntament d'Amer	Amer	08/11/2022
3	Ajuntament de Bàscara	Bàscara	04/10/2022
4	Ajuntament de Bescanó	Bescanó	17/10/2022
5	Ajuntament de Beuda	Beuda	08/09/2022
6	Ajuntament de Calonge i Sant Antoni	Calonge i Sant Antoni	30/09/2022

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
7	Ajuntament de Canet d'Adri	Canet d'Adri	17/10/2022
8	Ajuntament de Cassà de la Selva	Cassà de la Selva	04/11/2022
9	Ajuntament de Castellfollit de la Roca	Castellfollit de la Roca	21/11/2022
10	Ajuntament de Colomers	Colomers	20/10/2022
11	Ajuntament Cornellà del Terri	Cornellà del Terri	23/11/2022
12	Ajuntament de Forallac	Forallac	02/11/2022
13	Ajuntament de Fornells de la Selva	Fornells de la Selva	17/10/2022
14	Ajuntament de Girona	Girona	11/10/2022
15	Ajuntament de Gombrèn	Gombrèn	17/10/2022
16	Ajuntament de Gualta	Gualta	14/10/2022
17	Ajuntament de Juià	Juià	26/11/2022
18	Ajuntament de la Bisbal d'Empordà	La Bisbal d'Empordà	17/10/2022
19	Ajuntament de la Cellera de Ter	La Cellera de Ter	07/11/2022
20	Ajuntament de la Tallada d'Empordà	Tallada d'Empordà	04/10/2022
21	Ajuntament de la Vall d'en Bas	Sant Esteve d'en Bas	07/11/2022
22	Ajuntament de Les Preses	Les Preses	03/10/2022
23	Ajuntament de Lladó	Lladó	07/11/2022
24	Ajuntament de Llagostera	Llagostera	17/10/2022
25	Ajuntament de Llambilles	Llambilles	18/10/2022
26	Ajuntament de Llançà	Llançà	11/10/2022
27	Ajuntament de Maçanet de Cabrenys	Maçanet de Cabrenys	06/10/2022
28	Ajuntament de Madremanya	Madremanya	18/10/2022
29	Ajuntament de Mont-ras	Mont-ras	21/11/2022
30	Ajuntament d'Ogassa	Ogassa	25/10/2022
31	Ajuntament d'Olot	Olot	14/11/2022
32	Ajuntament de Palafrugell	Palafrugell	29/09/2022
33	Ajuntament de Palau de Santa Eulàlia	Palau de Santa Eulàlia	09/11/2022

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
34	Ajuntament de Palau-sator	Palau-sator	13/10/2022
35	Ajuntament de Pardines	Pardines	19/10/2022
36	Ajuntament de Peralada	Peralada	07/11/2022
37	Ajuntament de Planoles	Planoles	07/10/2022
38	Ajuntament de Porqueres	Porqueres	09/11/2022
39	Ajuntament de Portbou	Portbou	09/11/2022
40	Ajuntament de Quart	Quart	25/10/2022
41	Ajuntament de Regencós	Regencós	13/10/2022
42	Ajuntament de Riells i Viabrea	Riells i Viabrea	03/11/2022
43	Ajuntament de Ripoll	Ripoll	03/10/2022
44	Ajuntament de Sant Andreu Salou	Sant Andreu Salou	19/10/2022
45	Ajuntament de Sant Aniol de Finestres	Sant Aniol de Finestres	09/11/2022
46	Ajuntament de Santa Pau	Santa Pau	08/11/2022
47	Ajuntament de Sant Climent Sescebes	Sant Climent Sescebes	18/10/2022
48	Ajuntament de Sant Hilari Sacalm	Sant Hilari Sacalm	09/11/2022
49	Ajuntament de Sant Joan de les Abadesses	Sant Joan de les Abadesses	06/10/2022
50	Ajuntament de Sant Joan de Mollet	Sant Joan de Mollet	08/11/2022
51	Ajuntament de Sant Julià de Ramis	Sant Julià de Ramis	14/11/2022
52	Ajuntament de Sant Martí de Llémena	Sant Martí de Llémena	14/11/2022
53	Ajuntament de Sant Miquel de Campmajor	Sant Miquel de Campmajor	02/11/2022
54	Ajuntament de Sant Miquel de Fluvià	Sant Miquel de Fluvià	07/11/2022
55	Ajuntament de Sant Pau de Segúries	Sant Pau de Segúries	19/10/2022
56	Ajuntament de Sarrià de Ter	Sarrià de Ter	27/09/2022
57	Ajuntament de Setcases	Setcases	11/11/2022
58	Ajuntament de Torrent	Torrent	13/10/2022
59	Ajuntament d'Ullà	Ullà	25/11/2022

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
60	Ajuntament d'Ullastret	Ullastret	08/11/2022
61	Ajuntament de Vallfogona del Ripollès	Vallfogona del Ripollès	17/10/2022
62	Ajuntament de Vidrà	Vidrà	27/09/2022
63	Ajuntament de Vilablareix	Vilablareix	18/10/2022
64	Ajuntament de Viladamat	Viladamat	12/10/2022
65	Ajuntament de Vilademuls	Vilademuls	04/10/2022
66	Ajuntament de Vilafant	Vilafant	29/09/2022
67	Ajuntament de Vilobí d'Onyar	Vilobí d'Onyar	16/11/2022
68	Ajuntament de Tortellà	Tortellà	28/11/2022
69	Ajuntament de Pontós	Pontós	29/11/2022
70	Ajuntament de Riudellots de la Selva	Riudellots de la Selva	30/11/2022
71	Ajuntament de Pals	Pals	22/11/2022
72	Ajuntament de Cabanes	Cabanes	1/12/2022
73	Ajuntament de Vila-sacra	Vila-Sacra	1/12/2022
74	Ajuntament de Meranges	Meranges	5/12/2022
75	Ajuntament de Garrigoles	Garrigoles	1/12/2022
76	Ajuntament de Celrà	Celrà	1/12/2022
77	Ajuntament de Vidreres	Vidreres	19/12/2022
78	Ajuntament de Rupià	Rupià	27/10/2022
79	Ajuntament de Blanes	Blanes	19/01/2023
80	Ajuntament d'Agullana	Agullana	17/01/2023
81	Ajuntament de Sales de Llierca	Sales de Llierca	17/01/2023
82	Ajuntament de La Pera	La Pera	23/01/2023
83	Ajuntament de Vilopriu	Vilopriu	23/01/2023
84	Ajuntament de La Vall de Bianya	La Vall de Bianya	07/11/2022
85	Ajuntament de Pont de Molins	Pont de Molins	15/12/2022
86	Ajuntament de Serinyà	Serinyà	12/12/2022

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
87	Ajuntament de Sant Jordi Desvalls	Sant Jordi Desvalls	05/12/2022
88	Ajuntament de Maià de Montcal	Maià de Montcal	30/11/2022
89	Ajuntament d'Anglès	Anglès	28/11/2022
90	Ajuntament d'Esponellà	Esponellà	16/11/2022
91	Ajuntament de Palol de Revardit	Palol de Revardit	16/11/2022
92	Ajuntament de Capmany	Capmany	24/01/2023
93	Ajuntament de Sant Julià del Llor i Bonmatí	Sant Julià del Llor i Bonmatí	25/01/2023
94	Ajuntament de Sant Gregori	Sant Gregori	25/01/2023
95	Ajuntament de Cistella	Cistella	25/01/2023
96	Ajuntament de Vilanant	Vilanant	26/01/2023
97	Ajuntament de Begur	Begur	31/01/2023
98	Ajuntament de Queralbs	Queralbs	31/01/2023
99	Ajuntament de Sant Feliu de Guíxols	Sant Feliu de Guíxols	08/11/2022
100	Ajuntament d'Avinyonet de Puigventós	Avinyonet de Puigventós	31/01/2023
101	Ajuntament d'Aiguaviva	Aiguaviva	07/02/2023
102	Ajuntament de Torroella de Montgrí	Torroella de Montgrí	01/07/2023
103	Ajuntament de Bellcaire d'Empordà	Bellcaire d'Empordà	06/02/2023
104	Ajuntament de Santa Cristina d'Aro	Santa Cristina d'Aro	15/11/2022
105	Ajuntament de Sant Llorenç de la Muga	Sant Llorenç de la Muga	07/01/2023
106	Ajuntament de Parlavà	Parlavà	08/02/2023
107	Ajuntament de Das	Das	09/02/2023
108	Ajuntament de Verges	Verges	02/03/2023
109	Ajuntament de Vall-llobrega	Vall-llobrega	25/02/2023
110	Ajuntament de Puigcerdà	Puigcerdà	25/03/2023

3.4 Follower regions

Through an open call, the project selected 7 follower regions so they can learn from the experiences of the 3 pilot regions that have already made significant progress in renewable energy development. The goal is to facilitate knowledge transfer and collaboration between pilots and follower regions (via study visits, peer to peer support, and tailored webinars and workshops), enabling the followers to adopt best practices and implement renewable energy strategies in their own territories.

The selected authorities and energy agencies signed a MoA and follow ePLANET's mission to improve the coordination between local authorities and regional governments to optimise decision-making processes, coherence, and consistency with respect to implementing energy transition measures in towns and cities.

Table 3-4 shows which are these 7 selected follower PAs as well as the dates when they signed the MoA.

Table 3-4- Status of signed MoAs by the follower regions

ID number	Organisation	Place	Date
1	Agency for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Protection	Bucharest (Romania)	25/07/2022
2	Consell Comarcal del Baix Llobregat	Sant Feliu de Llobregat (Spain)	25/07/2022
3	South East Energy Agency ¹	Kilkenny (Ireland)	26/07/2022
4	Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia	Thessaloniki (Greece)	26/07/2022
5	Municipality of Fyli	Ano Liosia (Greece)	01/08/2022
6	Comunidade Intermunicipal do Tâmega e Sousa	Penafiel (Portugal)	08/08/2022
7	Union of Bulgarian Black Sea Local Authorities	Varna (Bulgaria)	22/08/2022

¹ Formerly known as 3 Counties Energy Agency (3CEA) during the application process.

4 Final considerations

The MoA serves as a formal agreement among participating entities, such as local and regional authorities, to collaborate and work together towards the objectives of the ePLANET project. It signifies a commitment to joint efforts and cooperation in achieving common goals related to energy transition.

Through the MoA, participating authorities express their commitment to align their energy transition plans and actions with national priorities. This ensures a coordinated approach and promotes consistency in the implementation of sustainable energy strategies.

Additionally, the MoA establishes a framework for institutionalizing the engagement of local and regional authorities in the ePLANET project. By signing the MoA, authorities demonstrate their intention to actively participate in the project's activities and contribute to its success.

The MoA also plays a role in scaling up ePLANET beyond the initial pilot territories. It outlines the process for involving additional local and regional authorities, facilitating the transfer and replication of successful practices and strategies to a wider geographic area. The MoA may involve not only local and regional authorities but also other relevant stakeholders, such as energy agencies, organizations, and community representatives. This broadens the engagement and ensures a diverse range of perspectives and expertise in the decision-making process.

As the MoA would be the forerunner of the ePLANET “Joint Agreement”, it is highlighted that it would be beneficial for the consortium to be proactive and to link these two documents in good time.

As of July 2023, a total of 199 MoAs have been signed, representing a significant step towards the ambitious target of 603. While progress has been made, further efforts are required to bridge the gap and achieve the desired outcome. In the next months, scaling up efforts will become a priority, with a focus on engaging potential stakeholders and establishing a clear roadmap with designated responsibilities to expedite progress.

Annex 1 - Memorandum of Adhesion (Pilot phase)

Organisation:

Place: / (City/Country)

We, the **(Name of Signatory Organisation)**, hereby declare our intention to support the uptake of results of the European project:

ePLANET (European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition) *

The **ePLANET** project is implemented in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and focuses on accelerating energy transition in the public sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities for the implementation of energy transition measures. The project targets the deployment of a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share information.

More specifically, we declare our intention to support the implementation of **ePLANET** activities and the uptake of the project results, within our reach of competence. In particular, we aim to:

- Participate in **ePLANET** networking, capacity building and dissemination **events** (e.g. meetings, webinars, stakeholders' forum etc.), so as to exchange experiences and knowledge on energy transition issues with other public bodies at regional, national and European Union (EU) level, identify common challenges and explore potential synergies;
- Provide **feedback** to support the development of the **ePLANET** platform and governance innovations, so as to maximise adoption and sustainability of the project outcomes beyond its duration;
- Exploit the **ePLANET tools** (e.g. **ePLANET** digital platform, a repository of best practices and solutions for energy transition, etc.) and outcomes and promote their implementation within the region, municipalities and other interested stakeholders in our territory / network;
- Utilize the **holistic methodology** developed in the **ePLANET** project to develop or improve realistic and economically affordable sustainable energy and climate action planning for the achievement of the energy transition targets;
- Strengthen our cooperation, through engaging in **ePLANET** activities, with the region, municipalities and other public bodies in our territory, supporting the **development of coordinated strategies** and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of new figures and roles within our organisation;
- Seek **synergies** between **ePLANET** and other relevant projects and initiatives implemented in our territory, aiming at multiplying the benefits.

We understand that, by signing this document, no financial or other liabilities from the **ePLANET** project or its partners shall occur.

Any personal data we may provide during our cooperation with the **ePLANET** consortium shall be treated confidentially for the exclusive use of the **ePLANET** project in accordance with the provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/779/EU – GDPR).

The Memorandum of Adhesion has both an English version and a local language version. Both versions are equally authentic.

Place – Date: -

(Organisation stamp)	(Signature of Representative)
	(Name and surname of Representative)

	<p>* The ePLANET H2020 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450.</p>
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Annex 2 - Memorandum of Adhesion (Replicability phase)

Organisation:

Place: / (City/Country)

We, the **(Name of Signatory Organisation)**, hereby declare our interest in becoming an **engaged stakeholder** of the European project:

ePLANET (European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition) *

The **ePLANET** project is implemented in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and focuses on accelerating energy transition in the public sector, by improving coordination between local and regional authorities for the implementation of energy transition measures. The project targets the deployment of a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share information.

More specifically, we declare our intention to support the implementation of **ePLANET** activities and the uptake of the project results, within our reach of competence, in case of a successful application. In particular, we aim to:

- Participate in ePLANET networking, capacity building and dissemination **events** so as to exchange experiences and knowledge on energy transition issues with other public bodies at regional, national and European Union (EU) level, identify common challenges and explore potential synergies;
- Provide **feedback** to support the development of the ePLANET platform and governance innovations, so as to maximise adoption and sustainability of the project outcomes beyond its duration;
- Exploit the ePLANET **tools** (e.g. ePLANET digital platform, a repository of best practices and solutions for energy transition, etc.) and outcomes and promote their implementation within the region, municipalities and other interested stakeholders in our territory / network;
- Support / promote the ePLANET **Joint Agreement**, which will constitute a major agreement between public authorities and interested stakeholders reflecting a joint vision on actions and initiatives to accelerate energy transition;
- Consider the Policy recommendations at the EU level that will be developed by ePLANET, towards future development and/or update of our local / regional **energy policies**;
- Strengthen our cooperation, through engaging in ePLANET activities, with the region, municipalities and other public bodies in our territory, supporting the **development of coordinated strategies** and action plans towards energy transition, potentially with the addition of **new figures and roles** within our organisation;
- Seek **synergies** between ePLANET and other relevant projects and initiatives implemented in our territory, aiming at multiplying the benefits.

We understand that, by signing this document, no financial or other liabilities from the ePLANET project or its partners shall occur.

Any personal data we may provide during our cooperation with the ePLANET consortium shall be treated confidentially for the exclusive use of the ePLANET project in accordance with the provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (2016/779/EU – GDPR).

The Memorandum of Adhesion has both an English version and a local language version. Both versions are equally authentic.

Place – Date: -

<p>(Organisation stamp)</p>	<p>(Signature of Representative)</p> <hr/> <p>(Name and surname of Representative)</p>
	<p>* The ePLANET H2020 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450.</p>

Template for MoA to support an application within the ePLANET project. Please print on the organisation's headed paper, scan to PDF and upload to the online application form

